

Reliability Growth Planning for Discrete-Use Systems

J. Brian Hall, Ph.D.; U.S. Army Evaluation Center

Key Words: Reliability Growth, Planning, Growth Potential

SUMMARY & CONCLUSIONS

In the recent past, the Defense Science Board (DSB) Task Force report on Developmental Test and Evaluation [1] revealed a significant increase in the number of DoD weapon system programs evaluated as not being operationally suitable. The primary reason is the lack of material readiness due to poor system Reliability, Availability, and Maintainability (RAM). The report shows that nearly half of U.S. Army systems from 1997-2006 failed to demonstrate their established reliability requirements during Operational Testing. As a result of the DSB findings and associated DoD Reliability Improvement Working Group (RIWG) report [2], a series of department policies have been established that place increased emphasis not only on reliability growth planning and tracking, but also on reliability best practices [3], and reliability language for defense acquisition contracts [4, 5]. As such, it is now department policy [6, 7] “for programs to be formulated to execute a viable RAM strategy that includes a reliability growth program as an integral part of design and development.” The most recent policy [8] further stipulates, “For new or restructured programs DOT&E will not approve TESs and TEMPs lacking a reliability growth curve or software failure profile.”

This paper presents a detailed Reliability Growth (RG) planning approach that may be utilized for developing RG programs for discrete-use systems, thereby facilitating the implementation of the aforementioned DoD reliability policies. More specifically, this approach, hereafter referred to as PM2-Discrete, may be utilized for developing RG programs and associated planning curves that: (1) portray planned reliability achievement as a function of program resources; (2) serve as a baseline against which demonstrated reliability values may be compared throughout a test program (for tracking purposes); and (3) illustrate and quantify the feasibility of a test program in achieving interim and final reliability goals. In particular, PM2-Discrete possesses a series of management metrics that may be used to assess the effectiveness of proposed RG programs. These metrics serve as concomitant measures of programmatic risk and system maturity that may also be assessed during testing for progress reporting purposes. A methodology overview and application of PM2-Discrete is given, as well as an abbreviated overview of relevant literature within the area of RG planning. Note that derivations of the model equations (not presented herein), are available and may be referenced in [9].

ACRONYMS

AEC	– Army Evaluation Command
AMSAA	– Army Materiel Systems Analysis Activity
CAP	– Corrective Action Period
DOT&E	– Director, Operational Test and Evaluation
FEF	– Fix Effectiveness Factor(s)
FOT	– First Occurrence Trial(s)
iid	– Independent and Identically Distributed
LCB	– Lower Confidence Bound
MLE	– Maximum Likelihood Estimation/Estimate(s)
PDF	– Probability Density Function
TES	– Test and Evaluation Strategy
TEMP	– Test and Evaluation Master Plan

NOTATION

k	– total number of potential failure modes
m	– total number of observed failure modes
n	– beta shape parameter for pseudo trials
x	– beta shape parameter for pseudo failures
T	– total number of trials
$N_{i,j}$	– number of failures for mode i in trial j
N_i	– total number of failures for mode i
P_i	– prob. of occurrence of failure mode i
d_i	– FEF for failure mode i
t_i	– FOT of failure mode i
R_I	– expected initial reliability
R_A	– portion of R_I comprised of A-modes
R_B	– portion of R_I comprised of B-modes
R_{GP}	– reliability growth potential
$\mu(t)$	– expected failure modes on trial t
$\phi(t)$	– expected fraction surfaced on trial t
$h(t)$	– expected probability of failure on trial t
$R(t)$	– expected reliability on trial t

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

The genesis of RG planning is marked by a paper written by Selby and Miller [10] who were the first researchers to apply the Duane Postulate [11] for planning reliability achievement as a function of test time under concurrent failure mode mitigation. A number of early RG planning models, or “first generation models,” have been based on the Duane

Postulate, e.g., the Military Handbook 189 planning model [12], AMSAA's System Planning Model [13], and AMSAA's Subsystem Planning model [14]. Whilst all of these RG planning models are for continuous-use systems and have proven to be useful over the years there are notable technical shortcomings of methods based on the Duane Postulate. These technical issues, outlined in ATEC IPG 09-1 [15], have not only been observed from decades of lessons learned in RG planning but also constitute the impetus for advancing second generation models like PM2-continuous [16, 17] and its discrete analogue presented herein.

1.2 Overview

This paper is organized as follows. The methodology is presented in Section 2, which consists of a list of assumptions, an overview of the RG planning process, and an outline of the model equations for which PM2-Discrete is based. The proposed RG planning methodology is illustrated via a simple application in Section 3. Emphasis is placed on how the RG management metrics may be utilized to assess the effectiveness of potential RG programs. Mitigating typical producer and consumer risks in the test design and analysis process is also addressed.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Assumptions

1. Initial failure probabilities p_1, \dots, p_k constitute a realization of an iid random sample P_1, \dots, P_k such that $P_i \sim \text{Beta}(n, x)$ for each $i=1, \dots, k$. The PDF parameterization utilized herein is given as,

$$f(p_i) \equiv \begin{cases} \frac{\Gamma(n)}{\Gamma(x) \cdot \Gamma(n-x)} \cdot p_i^{x-1} \cdot (1-p_i)^{n-x-1} & p_i \in (0, 1) \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where n represents pseudo trials, x represents pseudo failures, and $\Gamma(x) \equiv \int_0^\infty t^{x-1} \cdot e^{-t} dt$ denotes the Euler gamma function.

2. The number of trials t_1, \dots, t_k until failure mode first occurrence constitutes a realization of a random sample T_1, \dots, T_k such that $T_i \sim \text{Geometric}(p_i)$ for each $i=1, \dots, k$.

3. The distribution of the number of system-level failures observed in fixed length constant configuration test phases follows from a binomial random variable.

2.2 Model Equations

2.2.1 Expected Number of Correctable Failure Modes

A quantity of immediate interest when developing a potential RG plan is the number of correctable failure modes, or B-modes, that the growth program may uncover if executed. The expected number of B-modes observed on or before trial t is expressed as,

$$\mu(t) \equiv n \cdot \ln R_B [\psi(n) - \psi(n+t)] = \sum_{j=0}^{t-1} \frac{\ln R_B^{-n}}{n+j} \quad (2)$$

where $n \in \mathbb{N}^+$ is the shape parameter of the beta distribution representing pseudo trials, R_B represents the portion of system reliability comprised of B-modes, and $\psi(n) \equiv \Gamma'(n)/\Gamma(n)$ denotes the psi gamma function evaluated at n . The right-hand-side (r.h.s.) of Equation (2) is derived from the well-known recurrence formula for the following difference in psi gamma functions,

$$\sum_{j=0}^{t-1} \frac{1}{n+j} = \psi(n+t) - \psi(n) \quad (3)$$

The resulting alternative, but identical, summation expression in Equation (2) allows one to utilize this model in software programs, like Microsoft Excel, that may not have psi gamma and gamma functions built-in. Note that the parsimonious formulae for the parameters n and R_B are given below. Finally, note that Wolman [18] was the first researcher to employ a failure mode classification scheme to distinguish between failure modes that are corrected and those that are not corrected.

2.2.2 Fraction Surfaced

Understanding program management's ability to impact the system's failure intensity via the corrective action effort is another important consideration. This is achieved via a metric that for convenience shall hereafter be referred to as the fraction surfaced. The associated model equation is given by,

$$\phi(t) \equiv \frac{1 - R_B^{\frac{t-1}{n}}}{1 - R_B} \quad (4)$$

where R_B and n are given by (10) and (12) below and R_t is the initial reliability goal specified by the practitioner. The fraction surfaced quantifies the expected probability of failure on trial t due a repeat B-mode and is expressed as a fraction of initial system unreliability. Thus, it expresses the fractional contribution associated with the known B-modes. Ellner and Wald [19] were the first researchers to advance this important metric.

2.2.3 Probability of Failure due to a New Failure Mode

In RG planning for continuous-use systems, e.g., Ellner and Hall [16, 17], a common measure of programmatic risk consists of the rate of occurrence of new B-modes at test time t . The discrete analogue is the expected probability of failure on trial t due to a new B-mode and its model equation is expressed as,

$$h(t) \equiv 1 - R_B^{\frac{n}{n+t-1}} \quad (5)$$

where n and R_B are given below. This expression estimates the expected probability of discovering a new B-mode on trial t . Thus, as the development effort continues, we would like the estimate of $h(t)$ to grow small, e.g., $h(t) \rightarrow 0$ as $t \rightarrow \infty$. Small values of $h(t)$ indicate that program management has observed the dominant failure modes in the system. Conversely, large values of $h(t)$ indicate higher programmatic risk w.r.t. additional unseen B-modes inherent

to the system. Effective management and goal-setting of $h(t)$ are good practices to reduce the likelihood of the customer encountering unknown failure modes during fielding and deployment.

2.2.4 Expected Reliability

Perhaps the most popular metric of interest includes the expected reliability on trial t under instantaneous failure mode mitigation. The expected reliability on trial t is expressed as,

$$R(t) \equiv R_A \cdot R_B^{1-\mu \left(\frac{t-1}{n+t-1} \right)} \quad (6)$$

where the formulae for R_A , R_B , and n are given below and μ is program management's fix effectiveness goal. Equation (6) is one of the most important model equations, as it is utilized to generate the idealized curve on the RG plan. The idealized curve is a central focal point since reliability targets are derived from it for test events included in the growth program.

2.2.5 Reliability Growth Potential

The earliest notion of the reliability growth potential of a system was first advanced in a paper written by Virene in 1968 [20]. The concept was adopted further by other researchers, and is a characteristic of a number of RG models; some include [9, 16, 17, and 19]. The growth potential represents the theoretical upper limit on reliability achieved by finding and effectively correcting all B-modes via an average level of fix effectiveness, μ . The RG potential for PM2-Discrete is derived by taking the limit of $R(t)$ from Equation (6) as $t \rightarrow \infty$. This limit yields the following result,

$$R_{GP} \equiv \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} R(t) = R_I^{1-MS \cdot \mu} \quad (7)$$

where the formula for R_I is given below, MS is program management's goal for the fraction of the failure intensity addressed, and μ is the planned average fix effectiveness. The interpretation of Equation (7) is that if program management tested the system forever, e.g., $t \rightarrow \infty$, and found every failure mode, then the theoretical upper limit on reliability that could be reached is only a function of three quantities, namely, the initial reliability of the system, the fraction of the failure intensity addressed, and how effectively associated failure B-modes are mitigated.

2.2.6 Formulae for Model Parameters

There are a number of model parameters utilized in the equations presented above that shall now be defined. Among these include: R_I , R_A , R_B , MS , and n . The initial reliability, R_I , is expressed as,

$$R_I \equiv R_A \cdot R_B \quad (8)$$

where R_A and R_B are the portions of system reliability comprised of failure modes that will not, and will be addressed by corrective action respectively. An equivalent expression for Equation (8), namely $\ln R_I = \ln R_A + \ln R_B$, is utilized to define the fraction of the system failure intensity addressed by the corrective action effort. This is also known as the Management Strategy and is given by,

$$MS \equiv \frac{\ln R_B}{\ln R_I} = \frac{\ln R_B}{\ln R_A + \ln R_B} \quad (9)$$

Using (9) the desired formula for R_B is found to be,

$$R_B = R_I^{MS} \quad (10)$$

Then by (8) and (10) the following expression for R_A is obtained,

$$R_A = \frac{R_I}{R_B} = \frac{R_I}{R_I^{MS}} = R_I^{1-MS} \quad (11)$$

Thus, from (10) and (11) it follows $R_A \cdot R_B = R_I^{1-MS} \cdot R_I^{MS} = R_I$ as desired. Also note that R_I is the initial reliability goal specified by the practitioner and thus a model input.

To derive a parsimonious expression for the beta parameter n , let R_G denote the final reliability goal, δ represent the lag time due to corrective action implementation, and T be the total number of trials in the RG program. Also, define $T_L \equiv T - \delta$, which denotes the trial number at the lag-time before the last corrective action period. In this case, $R(T_L)$ is interpreted as the final reliability that is achieved in the RG program. The desired formula for the parameter n is found as the solution to the equality, $R(T_L) = R_G$, where R_G is the final reliability goal for the system that is specified by the practitioner. The solution to the equality $R(T_L) = R_G$ may be conveniently expressed as the following function of R_I , R_G , R_{GP} and T_L ,

$$n = (T_L - 1) \cdot \frac{\ln(R_{GP} / R_G)}{\ln(R_G / R_I)} \quad (12)$$

Recall that the condition $n \in \square^+$ must hold for the model equations to exist. Notice if the reliability goal is chosen higher than the growth potential, i.e., chosen s.t. $R_G \geq R_{GP}$, then per Equation (12) $n \leq 0$. This emphasizes the importance for the practitioner to be mindful of the growth potential when specifying development goals for R_I , R_G , MS , and μ . Guidance on this is given in the application below.

Finally, this section is concluded with a summary of a few important points. First, notice that all of the model equations and model parameters presented above have now been expressed as simple functions in terms of planning parameters directly controlled by program management. These include the initial reliability goal, R_I , the final reliability goal, R_G , the fraction of the initial failure intensity planned to be addressed via the corrective action effort, MS , the goal average fix effectiveness, μ , the total number of trials in the RG program, T , and the lag-time due to corrective action implementation, δ . Second, all of these parameters are model inputs that must be specified by the practitioner. Guidance and rules-of-thumb on establishing goals for these quantities are provided in the application below. Lastly, note that the only additional model input is the reliability requirement, R_R . Thus, the reliability goal must be chosen higher than the requirement in order to mitigate typical producer and consumer risks.

3.1 Mitigating Consumer Risk

RG planning begins with structuring the reliability demonstration test for the requirement and backwards-planning. Per DA PAM 73-1 [21], “Both technical and operational RAM requirements are to be demonstrated with high statistical confidence.” This mandate for demonstrating RAM requirements via statistical confidence mitigates what is commonly known as the consumer risk. The consumer risk is a statistical Type II error, and in the context herein, is the probability that the Army accepts a system that does not meet its reliability requirement. When using a $(1-\alpha)\cdot 100$ percent LCB the risk of accepting a bad system is α . For a fixed-length constant configuration demonstration test, the one-sided LCB [22] on reliability of a discrete-use system is,

$$R_\alpha(a, b) = \frac{a - b}{a - b + (b + 1) \cdot F_\alpha [2 \cdot (b + 1), 2 \cdot (a - b)]} \quad (13)$$

where b failures are observed in a trials and F_α denotes the F-Ratio distribution with the specified degrees of freedom.

3.2 Mitigating Producer Risk

Another important consideration during RAM T&E planning is mitigating producer risk. The producer risk is a statistical Type I error and represents the risk that the Army rejects a system that meets its reliability requirement. The producer risk is assessed via Operating Characteristic (OC) curve analysis, e.g., see Ellner & Mioduski [23]. The procedure consists of the following steps which are illustrated by example:

- Step 1. Find the maximum allowable number of failure c such that the LCB is greater than the requirement,

$$R_\alpha(a, c) \geq R_r \quad (14)$$

For the presented application the requirement for the system is $R_r = 0.85$ and the demonstration test is planned to consist of 28 trials. Demonstrating the requirement with at least 80 percent statistical confidence, e.g., accepting at most $\alpha = 0.20$ consumer risk, one will find via (13) and (14) that the maximum allowable number of failures is $c = 2$.

- Step 2. Plot the OC curve using: (1) the maximum allowable number of failures $c = 2$ from Step 1 and; (2) the length of the test phase to demonstrate the requirement, i.e., 28 trials. The OC curve is generated via the Binomial CDF plotted as a function of single shot reliability,

$$P(X \leq c) \equiv \sum_{b=0}^c \binom{a}{b} \cdot p^b \cdot (1-p)^{a-b} \quad (15)$$

where p denotes the probability of failure. Figure 1 illustrates the OC curve based on (15) with $a = 28$ and $c = 2$.

- Step 3. Use the OC curve generated in Step 2 to select the final reliability goal R_G associated with the desired level of producer risk. In this example producer risk is limited to 30 percent and per Figure 1 the associated final reliability requirement is $R_G = 0.9316$. Thus, management would have about a 70 percent chance of successfully demonstrating the

$R_r = 0.85$ reliability requirement via 80 percent statistical confidence. Equivalently, this means that if the true reliability of the system is $R_G = 0.9316$, there is a 70 percent chance of observing the maximum allowable number of failures or less, e.g., $c \leq 2$, during the 28 trial demonstration test. Conversely, the probability of rejecting the system when it meets the requirement, i.e., the producer risk, is 0.30.

Figure 1. Operating Characteristic Curve.

3.3 Reliability Growth Potential

Another important consideration in RG planning is the level of aggressiveness in the growth program relative to the RG potential. Recall that the growth potential (7) is the theoretical upper-limit on system reliability achieved by finding and correcting all B-modes with a specified level of effectiveness, μ . A common rule-of-thumb in RG planning for continuous-use systems is that the ratio of the MTBF goal to the MTBF growth potential, i.e., M_G / M_{GP} be at least 0.60 for the program to be sufficiently motivated, but not greater than 0.80, which is overly aggressive, or higher risk. An analogous rule-of-thumb for discrete-use systems is expressed as,

$$\frac{M_G}{M_{GP}} = \frac{1/(1-R_G)}{1/(1-R_{GP})} = \frac{(1-R_{GP})}{(1-R_G)} \in [0.60, 0.80] \quad (16)$$

where the interpretation of M_G and M_{GP} are mean rounds between failure and its growth potential, respectively. Note that the general guidelines above are not formal axioms but are simply rules-of-thumb. Thus, the practitioner should be cognizant of this ratio and it is recommended (not required) it be set within the interval above. For the application herein, this ratio is set at 0.70. This is utilized in the next section to obtain the initial reliability goal for the system.

3.4 Finding the Initial Reliability Goal

RG plans are often developed before test articles are available, which presents the need to establish a system-level initial reliability goal, R_I . This value represents the nexus between Design for Reliability (DFR) work and a traditional RG test program, as R_I is the reliability goal for the DFR program and also the initial system-level reliability target to be demonstrated in the first phase of the growth program. By

setting Equation (16) to 0.70 as discussed above the following expression is obtained which gives a goal growth potential,

$$R_{GP} = 1 - 0.70 \cdot (1 - R_G) = 0.9521 \quad (17)$$

where $R_G = 0.9316$ was determined by the OC curve analysis above. Then by establishing development goals for the management strategy and average fix effectiveness, the RG potential formula may be utilized to obtain the initial reliability goal. In this application, program management is planning to address 98 percent of the failure intensity with 80 percent average fix effectiveness, i.e., $MS = 0.98$ and $\mu = 0.80$. Using these development goals and setting (17) to (7) yields the following expression for the initial reliability,

$$R_i = R_{GP}^{1/(1-MS \cdot \mu)} = 0.7968 \quad (18)$$

Thus, over a sequence of Developmental and Operational Tests the RG program is structured to grow system reliability from $R_i = 0.7968$ to $R_G = 0.9316$. The next aspect of RG planning is to determine the number of test phases, number of trials in each test phase, and number of Corrective Action Periods, or CAPs, to incorporate.

3.5 Developmental Test Planning

Systematic failure mode mitigation constitutes the ethos of the RG process. Clearly, this process involves finding, analyzing, and effectively correcting reliability deficiencies discovered during developmental and operational testing. Thus, configuring a RG program, i.e., finding the number of test phases, number of shots per phase, number of scheduled CAPs, as well as how to position the CAPs, is fundamentally based on the rate of occurrence of correctable failures, or B-modes, that are anticipated at various stages throughout testing. Whilst there are several ways to structure a RG test program, a natural method consists of scheduling CAPs at the end of preceding test events whereby a desired number of B-modes are anticipated to be observed and corrected in each. In this application, 4 test phases, and 4 CAPs are planned prior to the demonstration test discussed above. These tests are structured s.t. at least 2 expected B-modes are uncovered and fixed in each CAP. To determine the length of each test event, Equation (2) is utilized to estimate the total cumulative number expected number of B-modes by trial t . Based on Equation (2) defined by the planning parameters and development goals defined above, 2 B-modes are expected by trial 12, 4 B-modes are expected by trial 31, 6 B-modes are expected by trial 65, and 8 cumulative B-modes are expected by trial 121. Planning for a $\delta = 2$ shot corrective action lag, the first test phase would need to be 14 trials with CAP1 immediately following. The second test phase would need to be 19 shots with CAP2 immediately following trial 33. The third test phase would need to be 34 shots with CAP3 after trial 67. Finally, the fourth test phase would need to be 56 shots with CAP4 after trial 123.

3.6 Assessing the Effectiveness of the RG Program

One of the benefits of the presented approach is that it possesses a series of RG management metrics that may be

utilized to assess the effectiveness of potential RG programs. The first metrics of basic interest include management's development goals with respect to the fraction of the failure intensity planned to be addressed, how effectively associated failure modes are planned to be mitigated, and the planned turn-around time for corrective action implementation. In this application, $MS = 0.98$, $\mu = 0.80$, and $\delta = 2$ shots, which are reasonable goals. $MS \in [0.90, 1.00]$ and $\mu \in [0.7, 0.8]$ are some general rules-of-thumb for discrete-use systems. The metric, $\mu(t)$ given by Equation (2), provides insight into the expected number of correctable failure modes that are anticipated to be observed if the RG program were executed. In this application $\mu(T_L = 121) = 8$ major redesigns are anticipated, provided the development goals above are achieved. $\phi(t)$ given by Equation (4), is utilized to estimate the fractional amount that these 8 B-modes contribute to the initial failure probability. In this application $\phi(T_L = 121) = 0.8734$ which means that program management is expected to be able to impact a significant portion of the initial failure probability by implementing fixes to the 8 anticipated B-modes. Another metric of interest is $h(t)$ given by Equation (5). In this application, the probability of observing a new B-modes is expected to be reduced from about 20 percent in the first trial to about 2.7 percent in trial $T_L = 121$. Conditioned on achieving the development goals above, expected system reliability $R(t)$ given by Equation (6) is anticipated to grow from $R_i = 0.7968$ to $R_G = 0.9316$. Recall that the RG potential is $R_{GP} = 0.9521$ per Equation (7) so the ratio of $(1 - R_{GP}) / (1 - R_G) = 0.7$ is consistent with known rules-of-thumb. Note that the final reliability goal $R_G = 0.9316$ was established via OC curve analysis (illustrated in *Figure 1*) s.t. the producer risk is mitigated to 0.30 and the consumer risk is mitigated to 0.20. Lastly, note that plots of the metric curves associated with Equations (2), (4), (5), and (6) are readily available but suppressed herein due to space limitations.

3.7 Portraying the RG Planning Curve

Figure 2 below illustrates the RG planning curve developed for the application discussed above. A summary of relevant features follow:

- The goal of the RG program is to grow from $R_i = 0.7968$ to $R_G = 0.9316$ in order to demonstrate the user's 0.85 reliability requirement via 80 percent statistical confidence.
- 5 test phases need to be conducted whose lengths should be at least 14, 19, 34, 56, and 28 trials in duration, respectively. Additionally, 4 CAPs should be scheduled after trials 14, 33, 67, and 123.
- Under competitive prototyping [24], each vendor should plan to mature the initial designs of their prototypes to reach an initial reliability of $R_i = 0.7968$.
- The vendors (on average) need to address about 98 percent of the system's initial failure intensity via corrective action, do so with 80 percent average fix effectiveness, and work to achieve a $\delta = 2$ shot corrective action lag on average.

Finally, note that there is no such thing as an inaccurate RG plan, as the growth program is configured by backwards-planning from user's requirement. Thus, for reliability achievement to be on track, it must get on and stay on the RG curve. Also, if a vendor falls short of a given reliability target, it is not that the RG curve was based on bad assumptions, as the RG curve did exactly what it was intended to do which is identify when reliability achievement is on or off track.

Figure 2. PM2-Discrete RG Planning Curve.

REFERENCES

1. U.S. Department of Defense, "Defense Science Board Task Force Report on Developmental Test & Evaluation," Washington, DC: Government Printing Office, 2008.
2. U.S. Department of Defense, "Report of the Reliability Improvement Working Group," Washington, DC: Government Printing Office, 2008.
3. Defense Acquisition University (2008), "AMSAA Reliability Program Scorecard," Available: <https://acc.dau.mil/CommunityBrowser.aspx?id=210483>
4. Defense Acquisition University (2008), "Sample Reliability Language for DoD Acquisition Contracts based on GEIA Standard 0009," Available: <https://acc.dau.mil/CommunityBrowser.aspx?id=219127&lang=en-US>
5. GEIA Standard 0009, "Standards on Reliability Program Standard for Systems Design, Development, and Manufacturing," GEIA, 2008.
6. U.S. Department of Defense, memorandum, 21 July 2008, "Reliability, Availability, and Maintainability Policy," Washington, DC: Government Printing Office.
7. U.S. Department of Defense, "Operation of the Defense Acquisition," DoD Instruction 5000.02," Washington, DC: Government Printing Office, 2008.
8. U.S. Department of Defense, memorandum, 24 November 2009, "Test and Evaluation (T&E) Initiatives," Washington, DC: Government Printing Office.
9. J.B. Hall, "Methodology for Evaluating Reliability Growth Programs of Discrete Systems," PhD Dissertation, University of Maryland, College Park, 2008.
10. J.D. Selby and S.G. Miller, "Reliability Planning and

- Management (RPM)," *Proceedings ASQC/SRE Seminar*, Milwaukee, WI: ASQC, 1970.
11. J.T. Duane, "Learning Curve Approach to Reliability Monitoring," *IEEE Transactions on. Aerospace*, Vol. 2, 1964, p.p. 563-566.
12. U.S. Department of Defense, "Reliability Growth Management," Military Handbook 189, Washington, DC: Government Printing Office, 1981
13. P.M. Ellner, W.J. Broemm, and W.J. Woodworth, "Reliability Growth Guide," Technical Report No. 652, AMSAA, 2000.
14. P.M. Ellner, M.J. McCarthy, D.E. Mortin, and D.M. Querido, "Developing a Subsystem Reliability Growth Program using SSPLAN," Technical Report No. 555, AMSAA, 1994.
15. U.S. Department of the Army, memorandum, 6 February 2009, "ATEC IPG 09-1, Reliability Growth Planning Methodology," Washington, DC: Government Printing Office, 2009.
16. P.M. Ellner, and J.B. Hall, "Planning Model based on Projection Methodology, Technical Report No. 2006-9, AMSAA, 2006.
17. P. M. Ellner and J. B. Hall, "An Approach to Reliability Growth Planning based on Failure Mode Discovery and Correction using AMSAA Projection Methodology," *IEEE Proc. RAMS*, 2005, pp. 271-277.
18. W. Wolman, "Problems in System Reliability Analysis," *Statistical Theory of Reliability*, Marvin Zelen Ed., Madison, Wisconsin: University of Wisconsin Press, 1963, pp. 149-160.
19. P.M. Ellner, and L.C. Wald, "AMSAA Maturity Projection Model," *IEEE Proc. RAMS*, 1995, pp. 174-181.
20. E. P. Virene, "Reliability Growth and Its Upper Limit," *IEEE Proc. RAMS*, 1968, pp. 265-270.
21. U.S. Department of the Army, "RAM Management, in DA PAM 73-1, Appendix K-5, Washington DC: Government Printing Office, 2003, pp. 214-215.
22. W. Nelson, "Analysis of Complete Data," in *Applied Life Data Analysis*, New York: Wiley, 1982, pp. 204-209.
23. P.M. Ellner and R. Mioduski, "Operating Characteristic Analysis for Reliability Growth Programs," Technical Report No. 524, 1992.
24. U.S. Department of Defense, "Prototyping and Competition," Washington, DC: Government Printing Office, 2007.

BIOGRAPHIES

J. Brian Hall, Ph.D.

Director; U.S. Army Evaluation Center, TEAE-REA
4120 Susquehanna Avenue
APG, Maryland 21005, United States of America

brian.hall@us.army.mil

Dr. Hall is the Division Chief for Aviation, Missiles, and C3I Systems in the RAM Directorate, AEC. Additional biographical information is available in [9].